

HeLa_xCT#29-08-22_Round3,
2-2. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round2,
7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round3,7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round5,
7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round2,2-2. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#29-08-22_
Round1(1min),19-19. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round1,7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round2,7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round4,7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#29-08-22_Round1(1min),5-5. scan_raw

SourceData_ExtFig6abg

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round1, 7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round4, 7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#29-08-22_Round1(1min), 1-1. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round2, 7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round2, 7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round1, 7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round1, 7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round5, 4-4. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#29-08-22_Round2, 9-9. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#29-08-22_Round4(1min), 5-5. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round3,7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round5,
7-7. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#29-08-22_Round3,
20-20. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round4,3-3. scan_raw

HeLa_xCT#22-07-22_Round1,
7-7. scan_raw